
DEPICTION OF BOURGEOISIE SOCIETY THROUGH CHETAN BHAGAT'S NOVEL "ONE NIGHT AT CALL CENTRE" AND FILM "HELLO"

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Abstract:

This article presents a critical preview of social status and middle class people. Chetan Bhagat is the most influential personalities among the contemporary Indian writes who correlates the literature comforts, consoles, illuminates and mirrors the human problems but also affirms and reinforces social Political and ideological stand points.

In the present generation, everyone has complaints about lack of time in their lives. In this scenario, Bhagat through his characters attempts to teach the society how to achieve success. "One Night at Call Center" "The book has been translated into Hindi and was published by Prabhat Prakash. It was translated to Sinhala by Dileepa Jayakody and published in 2009 as Halo! Halo!. The book was also adapted into a film titled 'Hello" in 2008. The film revolves around a group of six call center employees working a call center in Gurgaon, Haryana India.

In this paper we discuss the main themes of the novel according to my point of view. Themes involve the anxieties and insecurities of the young middle class, such as career, family conflicts, Betrayal, Financial Problems, Personal problems, class struggle, Domination. The main purpose of this paper is to bring the Chetan Bhagat's novel "One Night at Call Center" adapted into a film "Hello" in 2008.

Key Words: *Aspiration, Chetan Bhagat, Youth, Financial Issues, Middle Class Status, Struggle, Bourgeoisie, Proletariat.*

Chetan Bhagat very effectively has preserved above themes in his novel preserved love, sex, marriage and desire, hope, premarital relation and struggle of Indian youth that made Chetan Bhagat Indian's ever best seller Indian English Author Chetan Bhagat very well used the social sites and Gadgets in his novels. It

isn't just Indian youth yet additionally the adolescent in worldwide felt Chetan Bhagat as a great writer.

Chetan Bhagat was born in New Delhi in a middle class Punjabi family on the 22nd day in April. His father was an army man and his mother, a government employee in the Agriculture Department.

The main portion of his education was done at Delhi. He studied in the army Public school New Delhi. After that he chooses to do Mechanical institute of Technology, Delhi in 1995.

Chetan Bhagat is a popular Indian creator Bhagat is viewed as a young symbol as opposed to as only a creator. He is likewise a decent feature writer and composes sections for some driving papers. He isn't just a decent author yet additionally an inspirational orator and has given numerous persuasive addresses at numerous colleges, organization and companies.

I want to present some important themes in "One Night at call Center" written by Chetan Bhagat adapted into film 'Hello'. In this Novel or film all the characters are suppressed depressed and frustrated in their personal and professional life with their relationship, financial issues, Betrayal, individualism and middle class societies conflicts, bourgeoisie and working class people.

'Hello' is a tale about the events that happen one night at a call centre. A group of call center employees juggle their personal problems with a stream of unending. When a mysterious caller offers them a change to redeem themselves.

As I see it, the financial trouble of middle class are the same as those of families at both lower and higher incomes,

expect in emphasis. With somewhat higher incomes, they have a little more cushion for manipulation and hence needs without cash reserves or insurance protection as often as may be the experience of lower income families. In this story all the characters are suffering from financial problems and tensions. As a middle class people they survive lots of conflicts.

In "One night at call center" Bhagat shows to us how upper class people bourgeoisie treat working class people (proletariat) and their dominance. Class scuffle may occur due to different demands and goals of different groups of people. Those things can be said or related with Marxism and socialism, such as group of people of the same social and economy class. According to Marxism there two different classes bourgeoisie and proletariat. There has been a struggle between the two classes. This struggle is known as class struggle.

According to me the novel "One Night at Call Centre" is focuses on middle income group. We find some leading themes and some sub themes in this novel, but domination of bourgeoisie it is a prime themes. The book has won the national best-selling award in India and has also resulted in a huge blockbuster movie. As a working class people the six characters deal with the daily pressures of call centre

life while experiencing serious personal difficulty.

Powerful and affluent people uses common and poor people's ideas and skills to produce their product and develop their own business, with huge amount. And because of all this the poor are staying poor and the rich are getting wealthy. This is becoming a colossal problem in India. This is chief reason behind the non-development of our country.

The bourgeoisie plays a heroic role by revolutionizing industry and modernizing society, it also seeks to monopolize the benefits of this modernization by exploiting the property less proletarian and thereby creating revolutionary tensions. Proletariat designated the class of wage workers who were engaged in industrial production and whose chief source of income was derived from the sake of their labor power.

Proletariat designated the class of wage workers who were engaged in industrial production and whose chief source of income was derived from the sale of their labor power. Subhash Bakshi is the manager of the call center. He is a demanding boss while at his end he is almost non-productive for the call center under his management, "Connexions" is facing a downfall and people are afraid of being fired at anytime, or on a bigger extent the whole company could be shut

down. Bakshi is compared with Ravan who is an evil looking and evil doer. When Shyam goes to Bakshi to talk about the problem they are facing because of system error, Bakshi diverts the talk by tempting Shyam for promotion by showing him growth chart.

This general corporate practice is being emphasized. In the era of throat cut competition, it is very difficult for the feeling of insecurity results in depression and suppression. Esha Singh or Eliza is an ambitious girl who wants to become a model. When she finds that there is no way to become model, she runs away from home and join call center to fulfill her dreams to be a model. Esha has compromised by sleeping with a designer to get a modeling contract. But the boy turned out to be opportunistic as he betrays her by telling her that she can't become a model due to her height Esha frustrated due to this betrayal .

Radhika another woman character her call name is Regima Jones. She is also swinging in the swing of hope and despair. She is married. When her husband extra marital affair with other girl revealed. She became suppressed and upset. In this novel Bhagat criticizes our government and call centers in Vroom's voice "Our government doesn't realize this but Americans are using us. We are sacrificing an entire generation to service their call

centers”. Bhagat determinate draws parallels between United States attitude and the attitude of India’s governmental and managerial elites.

In this way the novel or film “One Night at Call Center “ movie “Hello” is based on the reality of the life of common people . The characters portrayed and betrayal here are taken from the real life. All these characters presented the problems of the different problems by six different people. The themes involve the anxieties and insecurities of the rising Indian middle class people including questions about career, family conflicts, changing the relationships of the young Indian middle class societies, upper and middle class struggle and domination.

Bhagat present through the novel or film. The problem and despairs hopes and Aspirations of the youth. In spite of dealing with the cruel realities of life his

works manage to maintain the sense of pure humor.

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